

Inter-Atrial Septal Aneurysm Ala M-Mode!

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Description

The above transesophageal echocardiogram (TEE) images were obtained as part of work-up for a cardiac source of embolus in a patient with stroke. The midesophageal view in figure A revealed a highly mobile interatrial septal aneurysm (IASA) with spontaneous right to left bubble shunting indicative of a patent foramen ovale (PFO). The IASA mobility is further demonstrated using TEE m-mode in the midesophageal view in figure B, revealing an exaggerated excursion of the fossa ovalis exceeding 1.5 cm. The aneurysmal fossa ovalis with a small superior communication is again demonstrated in the deep stomach view in figure C, while color flow Doppler across the septum in figure D demonstrated spontaneous left to right shunting.

Discussion

Interatrial septal aneurysm is a localized bulging of the fossa ovalis with excess excursion into the right or left atrium or both of approximately 1 cm [1]. IASA has been reported to result in significant atrial arrhythmias [2].

Atrial septal abnormalities, including PFO have been highly associated with ischemic stroke, especially in patients younger than 55 years [3]. Patients with both IASA and PFO in the setting of stroke are at a very high risk of recurrent stroke, mandating preventive therapies beyond aspirin alone [4].

Transcatheter occlusion of IASA with PFO in the setting of paradoxical embolism is safe and effectively eliminates shunting and atrial septal mobility [5], providing incremental prevention of recurrent embolic events compared with closure of isolated PFO.

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References

1. Olivares-Reyes A, Chan S, Lazar EJ, et al. Atrial septal aneurysm: a new classification in two hundred five adults. *J Am Soc Echocardiogr.* 1997 Jul-Aug;10(6):644-56.
2. Keieaty S, Al Balkhi A, Al-Nassar Q, et al. A large atrial septal aneurysm presenting with severe arrhythmias: A case report. *Int J Surg Case Rep.* 2025 Sep;134:111738.
3. Overell JR, Bone I, Lees KR. Interatrial septal abnormalities and stroke: a meta-analysis of case-control studies. *Neurology.* 2000 Oct 24;55(8):1172-9.
4. Mas JL, Arquizan C, Lamy C, et al; Patent Foramen Ovale and Atrial Septal Aneurysm Study Group. Recurrent cerebrovascular events associated with patent foramen ovale, atrial septal aneurysm, or both. *N Engl J Med.* 2001 Dec 13;345(24):1740-6.
5. Wahl A, Krumdsorf U, Meier B, et al. Transcatheter treatment of atrial septal aneurysm associated with patent foramen ovale for prevention of recurrent paradoxical embolism in high-risk patients. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2005 Feb 1;45(3):377-80.

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